

RECORDING HOLY QUR'AN AS A HYPNOPARENTING MEDIUM FOR BUILD CHARACTER AND INCREASE MOTIVATION IN CHILDREN

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Abstract.

Industrial revolution 4.0 is marked by the emergence of supercomputers, smart robots, driversless vehicles, genetic editing and the development of neurotechnology that allows humans to further optimize brain function (www.beritasatu.com). Hypnotherapy can be one method in optimizing brain function. Through hypnotherapy can help parents to shape the child's character by optimizing brain function. Hypnoparenting can be interpreted as child coaching by observing the influence of hypnosis to always inculcate a positive recording / suggestion on the subconscious mind of the child. The writing of this paper aims to explain the use of hypnoparenting in children as the process of formation of positive thinking patterns. In addition, this paper also aims to explain the use of technological progress and the use of the Qur'anic verse as an introduction to the hypnoparenting method. Hypnoparenting implementation model with the introduction of Recording Holy Quran is a model of support and fulfillment of psychological needs for children. Steps used in this activity is to listen to the holy verses of the Qur'an through Recording Holy Qur'an to deliver the child in a state of calm and enter the frequency of alpha brain waves or theta (trance condition). After that, parents give positive suggestive sentences that are heard near his ears. Thus, it is expected that negative programs embedded in their subconscious mind can be released, success programs can begin to be planted early on.

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1. Introduction

An educational observer from America Thomas Lickona precisely about the formation of cultural change at this time. There are at least 10 symptoms of the decline and triumph of countries, namely: (1) the behavior of adolescents and the community; (2) using abusive language, dirty, and ridicule; (3) the influence of friends and the environment exceeds family components; (4) illegal drugs and free sex; (5) the disappearance of moral values and truth in people's lives; (6) decreasing sense of nationality and nationalization; (7) low respect for children to parents and teachers; (8) the violence of mass media shows that damage the mentality of children; (9) fraud (corruption and manipulation) occur everywhere; and (10) the point of suspicion and hatred among fellow citizens.

If you look at the state of the younger generation, this shows about the Lickona criteria above. That is, children and young people as the next generation of young people are currently in an emergency. Theodore Roosevelt in Silawati (2015) said : “To educate a person in mind and not in morals is to educate a menace to society”

Families are also a small environment that can contribute greatly to character building and contributing motivation to children's achievement. Unfortunately, the role of the family is still being considered by some people, namely eliminating family responsibilities as forming characters and the biggest motivating contributor to children. Sustainable Development Goals or in English known as the Sustainable Development Goals with SDGs with 17 families that have been established by the United Nations (UN), which are two people used for everyday life and for different welfare (Goal 3) and Quality education by ensuring quality education that is decent and inclusive and encourages lifelong learning opportunities for everyone (Goal 4). So it is important to encourage education in the family so that efforts to educate the life of the nation are also by forming an environment that makes children feel prosperous and healthy.

Therefore efforts to educate and provide a prosperous life for children need to be a concern. The problem is that parents' current activities as a consequence of efforts to meet the family's economic welfare or socialite demands result in a lack of time for children. Even though parents with certain knowledge and abilities can change children's mindset and behavior. For example about solutions that can be done by parents to still be able to optimize their role as parents in the midst of their busy work, namely through the hypnoparenting method.

Hypnoparenting is not a new thing in the world of parenting, but in this case the author will provide an innovation that is expected to optimize the method. Recent research from Abdurrochman, Perdana, and Andhika (2008), shows that when listening to the Qur'anic verse there is a significant increase in brain waves generated before and after listening to the Qur'anic verses. The frequency of brain waves is an important thing in the implementation of hypnoparenting, that is what underlies the authors to combine the both with the hope of better and optimal results.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Hypnoparenting

Hypnoparenting comes from the words hypnosis and parenting. Hypnosis according to Lucy (2011) means an effort to optimize the empowerment of subconscious mental energy (in this case to communicate) by resting the energy of the conscious soul in children (mental communication) as well as on the cultivator (astral communication). Parenting means everything that deals with the duties of parents in educating, nurturing, and raising children. This child coaching consists of three fields, namely physical, mental, and spiritual. The start is from planning a pregnancy to adolescence by those around him (parents, guardians, teachers, etc.).

Thus hypnoparenting can be interpreted as child development by paying attention to the influence of hypnosis to always instill a positive recording / suggestion on the child's subconscious mind (Lucy, 2011). The minds of children who have not been able to think logically tend to respond to stimuli received without too much consideration. 95% of parents' words, actions and attitudes easily enter the subconscious minds of children as if without being filtered.

2.2. Research on Hypnoparenting

The relationship between parents and children will influence children's acceptance of socialized values (Lestari, 2016). The results of the study have confirmed that parent-child communication can affect overall family function and psychosocial well-being in children (Shek, 2000)

According to Frank Outlaw of "words" (sayings) action will occur. Continuous "actions" will give birth to "habits". Often the word 'hypnotherapy' is a question for many parents because it relates to belief. Hypnotherapy is of many uses as long as it knows how to use it. This has nothing to do with mysticism, there is no element of magic in it, and it is not coercion on children to obey whatever their parents do. This will be explained slowly in simple language and can be accepted by belief.

The information in the short-term memory if repeated repetition or rehearsal is carried out, it will be stored in long-term memory. In the long-term memory, the stored information can be used at a later time (Matlin, 1998). An information can be part of memory if there is a permanent functional and structural change in the brain. This change is known as plasticity. The term plasticity was first coined by William James in 1890. Plasticity is defined as the change in the neuron path that occurs in relation to experience because of a habit that is acquired (Byrne & Roberts, 2004)

Sigmund Freud and many other psychologists claim that the human mind is composed of the conscious and subconscious mind. The conscious and subconscious mind communicates each other. However, the subconscious mind is not always in line with the conscious mind. Sometimes, the subconscious mind already has its own "program", emotions, habits, and beliefs that have been embedded previously. Apparently, 88% of the subconscious mind influences human attitudes and behavior compared to their conscious minds.

Research from Abdurrochman (2007) shows that listening to murotal Al-Qur'an can improve calmness. This is evident from the significant increase in delta waves. Recent research from Abdurrochman., Perdana, and Andhika (2008), shows that when listening to the verses of the Qur'an there is a significant increase in brain waves produced before and after listening to the Qur'anic verses.

3. Analysis and Synthesis

Family can be analogous to a ship that will take its passengers to a destination. During the ocean, the ship does not continue to be in calm waters. Many things might befall the ship, such as waves, corals, whirlpools, bad weather and other obstacles. In this case, parents are the ship's captain who will take control of the ship to reach its destination. Waves, corals, whirlpools, and bad weather are described as things or obstacles that are external to parents. These external things can come from the neighborhood, school environment, play environment, and children's watching and reading.

Problems with children not only come from the external environment, but also from the family's internal environment. When a ship is strong and quality, it is likely that the ship will be able to deal with all obstacles. But when the ship is fragile, it will be very easy for obstacles to overcome it.

External factors are factors that are very difficult to control. Therefore parents should strengthen their internal factors. This can be done by parents by applying the right parenting for their children. Many criminal cases involve children and adolescents because of their lack of proximity to the family, especially parents. Any wrong way of educating can result in wrong understanding. Busyness for busy parents sometimes neglects them about a responsibility that is very important in educating, directing and motivating children. Some parents assume that when a child's physical / physical needs are met, the task is done. Whereas in addition to physical needs, there is a need that is very important for children, namely the need for psychic or inner. Some parents often neglecting it with the reason that they do not have much time to fulfill these psychological needs.

3.1. Hypnoparenting

Hypnoparenting can be an alternative for parents, especially for those who have extra work on their jobs. Hypnoparenting according to Lucy (2011) can be interpreted as coaching children by paying attention to the influence of hypnosis to always instill a positive recording / suggestion on the child's subconscious mind. The minds of children who have not been able to think logically tend to respond to stimuli received without too much consideration. 95% of parents' words, actions and attitudes easily enter the subconscious minds of children as if without being filtered. According to Frank Outlaw of "words" (sayings) action will occur. Continuous "actions" will give birth to "habits"

Sigmund Freud and many other psychologists claim that the human mind is composed of the conscious and subconscious mind. The conscious and subconscious mind communicates each other. However, the subconscious mind is not always in line with the conscious mind. Sometimes, the subconscious mind already has its own "program", emotions, habits, and beliefs that have been embedded previously. Apparently, 88% of the subconscious mind influences human attitudes and behavior compared to their conscious minds.

Often the word 'hypnotherapy' is a question for many parents because it relates to belief. Hypnotherapy is of many uses as long as it knows how to use it. This has nothing to do with mysticism, there is no element of magic in it, and it is not coercion on children to obey anything their parents do.

The information in the short-term memory if repeated repetition or rehearsal is carried out, it will be stored in long-term memory. In the long-term memory, the stored information can be used at a later time (Matlin, 1998). Atkinson (1999) explains that memory is the ability to enter (learning), store (retention), and cause (remembering) things that were past. An information can be part of memory if there is a permanent functional and structural change in the brain. This change is known as plasticity. The term plasticity was first coined by William James in 1890. Plasticity is defined as the change in the neuron path that occurs in relation to experience because of a habit acquired (Byrne & Roberts, 2004). "The Messenger of Allah. like to repeat the words he said three times to be understood." (Narrated by Muhammad bin Yahya, from Abu Qutaibah - Muslim ibn Qutaibah-of Abdullah bin al-Mutsani, from Tsumamah, originating from Anas bin Malik, may Allah be pleased with him). From some of these statements, there are several things that we can underline, namely about 'repetition' and 'habit'. Hypnoparenting is very closely related

to repetition and habits of positive suggestive sentences. Everything that is done repeatedly will make a habit, be it positive or negative. Likewise for children. To educate them, we don't have to wait when they understand. Teach early or since the baby to do the right thing, so that everything he does is embedded sub-consciously. Some processes are responsible for storing information in long term memory. This includes attention, repetition, and training (Ling & Catling, 2012). The relationship between parents and children will influence children's acceptance of socialized values (Lestari, 2016). Research results have confirmed that parent-child communication can affect overall family function and psychosocial well-being in children (Shek, 2000).

3.2. Utilization of Brain Waves

The activity of the human mind can be measured by a device called EEG. This EEG can monitor a person's brain waves related to his mind activity. There are 4 main areas of brain waves, namely Beta (active condition), Alfa (calm & focus condition), Teta (very calm condition), and Delta (sleep). Humans will be able to receive suggestions if the brain waves are in teta state. Then you can say someone will be hypnosis if you are in a state of half-sleep. But for children, in the alpha wave, where the child is relaxed, the child will be easier to suggest. Whenever a child is in a hypnosis condition? At least in a day the child enters hypnosis twice when he is going to sleep and after waking up. The rest of the children are in a hypnosis condition when they are enjoying their activities, such as playing games, playing, joking, chatting, praying, bathing, eating and as long as the child enjoys his activities.

interesting

Figure 1. Brain Waves

Child hypnotherapy is effective for improving child development because hypnosis directly enters the subconscious mind of children. Thus, negative programs embedded in their subconscious mind can be released. Success programs can also be started early.

3.3. Recording the Holy Qur'an as a means of introducing Hypnotherapy

It has been explained previously, that in the implementation of hypnoparenting a condition is needed in which the child is in a relaxed state with the frequency of the brain in a state of alpha or theta waves. This condition can occur when a child is asleep and when he wakes up. Holy Quran recording here serves to convey the child in such a state.

Research from Abdurrochman (2007) shows that listening to murotal Al-Qur'an can improve calmness. This is evident from the significant increase in delta waves. Recent research from Abdurrochman., Perdana, and Andhika (2008), shows that when listening to the verses of the Qur'an there is a significant increase in brain waves produced before and after listening to the Qur'anic verses. This means that the recitation of the Qur'an recitation can help parents to deliver their children to relax conditions with the brain frequency that supports hypnoparenting. Emotional conditions have an influence on a person's cognitive abilities.

Matlin in Hastjarjo 2008 stated the same thing, there are two kinds of emotional influence on memory, namely mood-congruent and mood-state dependent. Mood-congruent means that if the information entered and the mood in someone has something in common, then memory performance will be better. Mood-state dependent means that when the storage of information and recall has the same mood, memory performance will be better if the mood is different.

Neuron systems in humans that are closely related to cognitive functions are influenced by various things, one of which is emotion. By listening to the recitation of the Qur'anic verses along with the child, it can deliver the child and parents to a mood that tends to be the same so that it affects emotional conditions that affect a person's cognitive abilities.

Holy Qur'an recording can make it easier for parents to listen to the chanting of the Qur'anic verses to children. Because with the recording system, parents do not need to worry about their ability to read the Qur'an because the chanting is already in the form of recording.

3.4. The Hypnoparenting technique uses the Record Holy Qur'an as an Introduction

Before hypnoparenting, parents must make sure the child is in his room in a position ready to sleep. Or if the child is not in the room when it's time to sleep, parents can invite him in good language. Before going to bed, parents invite their children to listen to the verses of the Quran through recording holy Qur'an. It has been explained previously, that the recitation of Qur'anic verses will affect the increase in brain wave frequency even reaching the delta stage. Before entering the delta wave, parents can take advantage of momentum when brain waves are in theta state. This situation can be seen when the child starts to relax marked by the eyes that begin to fade in the seconds before sleep. This condition does not last long. Therefore parents must really pay attention to the right timing. Before arriving at these conditions, when listening together, parents can touching the child with soft caresses and other physical contact such as gentle pat and so on. This can strengthen children's attachment to parents. When the time is right, parents can do hypnoparenting.

In doing hypnoparenting, parents can say positive suggestive sentences near the child's ear so that the child can hear them well. In the pronunciation, use good constructive sentences. Bless the right words gently so as not to damage the child's relaxed condition.

"And be afraid of Allah those who if they leave behind them are weak children, whom they are concerned about (their welfare). Therefore let them fear Allah and let them say Qaulan Sadida, the true word "(Qur'an 4: 9).

"Then speak to both of you with Qulan Layina - gentle words ..." (Surat Thaha: 44).

In addition to the sentences that are true and gentle, the suggestive sentences should also be said clearly, firmly and made an impression.

أُولَئِكَ الَّذِينَ يَعْلَمُ اللَّهُ مَا فِي قُلُوبِهِمْ فَأَعْرِضْ عَنْهُمْ وَعِظْهُمْ وَقُلْ لَهُمْ فِي أَنْفُسِهِمْ قَوْلًا بَلِيغًا

"They are people who know what is in their hearts. therefore turn away from them, and give them a lesson, and say to them Qaulan Baligha, a statement that imprints on their souls. "(Surat an-Nissa: 63)

Sentences that are conveyed should also be sentences that are easily understood by children and sentences that are fun so that it can generate motivation in children.

"And if you turn away from them to obtain the blessings from their Lord that you hope for, then say to them Qaulan Maysura-Pronunciation is easy and pleasant" (Surat al-Isra: 28).

The above is about the nature of the sentence and how to convey it. Moreover, what is no less important than the application of hypnoparenting to children's education is the continuity of parents in carrying out the method. Because the hypnoparenting method is a parenting method that must be done repeatedly so that the understanding that parents want to instill into the subconscious of the child and stored in their long-term memory.

4. Conclusion

Based on the library search and the discussion above, the authors conclude that:

1. The use of hypnoparenting in children as a process of forming a positive mindset can be done by utilizing technological advances and the use of Qur'anic verses.
2. Utilizing the Record Holy Qur'an as an introduction to effective hypnoparenting methods to shape and direct the natural conditions of the child's mind in a relaxed state with the frequency of the brain in a state of alpha or theta waves, where new beliefs and positive suggestions can be planted.

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